

Summary of the Book *Tarocchi De Figura Mundi. The Game of the Spheres* by Nicholas of Cusa

The unpublished two-volume work *Tarocchi De Figura Mundi. The Game of the Spheres* by Nicholas of Cusa, written by Anuar Zacarías, addresses, from a philosophical, historical, and iconographic perspective, aspects that until now have remained unexplored of the fifty fifteenth-century engravings commonly known as the “Tarot of Mantegna”. For the first time in over five centuries, this research reveals the name of their true author — the renowned philosopher Nicholas of Cusa — correcting previous hypotheses regarding both this and other possible authors.

Although it is related to tarot and the Renaissance games of triumphs (*ludus triumphorum*), it constitutes a distinct game, one that appears to have marked a turning point in the conception of card games. Therefore, these two volumes hold significant relevance not only for the history of art, tarot, and gaming, but, above all, this research opens new horizons toward disciplines such as philosophy, theology, and the humanities, which may now incorporate this fascinating educational game into their fields of study. Moreover, it is equally relevant to the history of science, as the author proposes — through the game's dynamics — a model of the infinite cosmos, a theme also explored in Cusa's major philosophical works, which directly or indirectly influenced Copernicus, Kepler, Galileo, and Giordano Bruno, among others. Cusa laid the conceptual groundwork for the scientific revolution by questioning absolute certainties, proposing a dynamic, infinite, and centerless universe, and suggesting both the relativity of motion and the limitations of human knowledge — many aspects of which are mirrored in the dynamics and allegories of the so-called Tarocchi. In summary, these are allegorical images that bring us closer to profound philosophical insights, offering a complex vision of the Universe, while also inviting introspection and Christian mysticism, for all these currents converge in Cusan thought.

The author of the Tarocchi has remained a mystery, apparently since the time of its creation, and for centuries speculation has circulated about various possible authors. Among those suggested are the artists Andrea Mantegna, Lazzaro Bastiani, and Baldini; while, concerning intellectual authorship, names such as Ludovico Lazzarelli, Cardinal Bessarion, Pope Pius II, and Nicholas of Cusa himself have been proposed. Henri Brockhaus was the first to speculate on the possible authorship of Cardinals Cusa and Bessarion, though without solid foundations, leading authorities in art history such as Arthur M. Hind and Wilshire to later dismiss these hypotheses. However, the attribution to Nicholas of Cusa becomes unquestionable after a detailed study of the fifty original fifteenth-century allegories (Series E), further supported by historical and philosophical evidence, and by the encrypted name of Nicholas of Cusa hidden within seven engravings. The correspondences between the iconography and various passages from the cardinal's philosophical works are, in many cases, strikingly precise and compelling.

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On the other hand, the vast similarities between the allegorical *Game of the Sphere* described by Nicholas of Cusa and the Tarocchi lead us to think that they are, in fact, the same game. At first, certain descriptions by the cardinal do not seem to fully align, which is why some art scholars have dismissed this possibility; however, a deeper reading, approached with the philosophical (rather than historical) perspective that these images demand, opens the possibility of understanding them as one and the same game. Likewise, there is a work by Nicholas of Cusa that some philosophers and experts consider lost since the sixteenth century and which they directly associate with the *De ludo Globi* (“Game of the Sphere”): it is the *Libello de figura mundi* (“little treatise on the representation of the world”), which very likely could be a short book containing the fifty images of the so-called Tarocchi. For this reason, I have decided to choose this title as the name of the game. Furthermore, although it is not a tarot deck, its reminiscences and its popular connection to those cards suggested to me that I should continue using this word as a nickname for Cusa’s game. Cardinal Nicholas of Cusa was an avid reader of the Platonic tradition, Hermetic writings, and the works of Ramon Llull, influences that are clearly reflected in the themes and allegories of this game, which reveals itself as a device —a true machine of memory.

Nicholas of Cusa was born in Germany and died in what is now Italy, the two regions where these images mainly circulated between the fifteenth and seventeenth centuries. It is important to note that the original version that fully embodies the philosophy of the Platonic cardinal is the so-called Italian Series E. The other versions omit many crucial details necessary for grasping its profound philosophical background. Philosophy has often been neglected because of its complexity, and in the case of the Tarocchi, aesthetic considerations have been privileged over its deeper philosophical qualities. Moreover, the game has been used for cartomancy, witchcraft, and other practices foreign to its creator’s original intent. Thus, now that the name of its true author is about to be more widely disseminated, together with his philosophical vision, this game will regain much of its original meaning — and perhaps the same will occur when the authorship of the Tarot of Marseille and other similar games is eventually revealed.

This fascinating discovery is the result of several years of continuous study: in addition to my philosophical training at UNAM, in 2021 I restored the fifty original fifteenth-century engravings (previously published in a book and card deck); I memorized each one of them, taught workshops, and carried out an extensive study of specialized bibliography.